

ON THE COMPATIBILITY OF CARBON FIBRES IN NICKEL

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Abstract

Carbon fibre - metal composites are required for high specific strength and higher temperature use. It is very important to know the stability of the composite materials at high temperature.

This paper deals with the reaction between carbon fibre and nickel. Nickel was coated uniformly on the high strength PAN based carbon yarn by electro-plating method. The yarn consists of 2000 mono-filaments. The yarn was held at the range of 6000°C and 1200°C, for 20 minutes and 48 hours, and mono-filaments from the yarn were examined by a scanning electron microscope, X-ray diffraction and an electron probe micro-analyser.

The nickel and carbon migrated across the interface forming a "graphitized" zone. Similar phenomenon was found on pyrolytic carbon. The activation energy of graphitization was 39.7 kcal/mol, and the rate determining process should be diffusion of carbon atoms through nickel.

An attempt to prevent reaction between carbon and nickel was carried out on surface oxidized carbon fibre. On the fibre after holding at 1000°C for 1 hour, no reaction was found with scanning electron microscopic observation, X-ray diffraction analysis and E.P.M.A.

I. Introduction

Investigations were carried out on compatibilities between carbon mono-filaments and plated nickel at high temperature to determine stability in the carbon-nickel composite materials (1). Reaction phenomena between carbon mono-filaments and nickel were observed carefully on carbon fibre yarn electro-plated with nickel (2).

II. Experiments

PAN based high strength carbon fibre yarn was used in this work. It consists of 2000 mono-filaments of carbon fibres, and each mono-filament is about 8 microns in diameter.

It is important to obtain a dense and uniform nickel layer on the carbon fibre in the study of reaction phenomena between carbon fibre and nickel. Electrolytic plating technique was used for this experiment, as it is easy to control the nickel layer by electrolysis with the bath of NiSO_4 150 g/l, NH_4Cl 15 g/l, B_2O_3 15 g/l and water (3). Thickness (0.13 - 5 μ) of the layer was controlled by deposited time. The nickel coated carbon yarn was held at 600°C and 1200°C for 20 minutes and 48 hours under 2×10^{-5} Torr.

Scanning electron microscopic observation (1), X-ray diffraction analysis (4), electron probe microanalysis (4) and tensile strength measurement (1) on reacting phenomena were carried out on fibres from the carbon yarn held at high temperature (1). Preferred orientations of the crystallites in the original carbon fibre and in the nickel coated carbon fibre held at high temperature were observed also by X-ray diffraction (4).

To compare with it, pyrolytic carbon decomposed from hydrocarbon (methane) at 1850°C, was used also. Nickel was electro-plated on it, and the thickness was about 1 μ . Nickel coated pyrolytic carbon was held at high temperature and examined for the reacting phenomena to compare with the fibres (5).

III. Results and discussion.

Uniform and compact nickel layer on each mono-filament in the yarn is required to find reproducible phenomena by holding at high temperature. As the carbon yarn consists of 2000 mono-filaments which are very thin as 8μ , and has high electrical resistivity, it is difficult to make cathode current density uniform all over mono-filaments in the yarn. Excellent nickel layer was obtained under the condition as follows (2): 1) less tension on the yarn in the electrolyte bath was desirable. 2) carbon yarn was supported at both ends in the bath and applied same electric current on both ends, and the cathode current density was 0.1 Amp./dm^2 . Uniform nickel layer on each mono-filament was obtained as shown in Photo 1, (2).

Strength of mono-filaments in the yarn held at high temperature was measured, and the results are shown as Fig. 1, (1). No change was found on strength of fibres held at 600°C for 10 hours. Strength of fibres, however, decreased rapidly after holding over 700°C . Strength of fibres held at 800°C for 10 hours and 1000°C for 1 hour indicate about 1/10 comparing with original fibre. It will be suggested that the deterioration phenomenon was caused by interaction between nickel and carbon fibre (1).

Fibres were observed on the phenomenon by a scanning electron microscope as shown in Photo 2, (1). A white ring was found on the outside of the fibre. Another white ring migrated into the carbon fibre, and finally it aggregated in the center of the carbon fibre as a white area. It was found from careful observation that the inner white ring consisted of many white small islands. The area passed through by the white ring showed flaky appearance, and many white particles were dispersed in the area.

Carbon fibres held at high temperature were examined by an electron probe microanalyser to determine the concentration distribution of nickel and carbon (4). Distribution of nickel along the diameter of the fibre is shown in Fig. 2a. The white rings in Photo 2 were nickel rich area, though the height of the peak did not show 100% nickel directly. The line has some gradient at the edge of the white part in Photo 2. A model on distribution of nickel was suggested as a thin line in Fig. 2 deduced from Photo 2 to analyse the result. The diameter of the spot of electron beam was about 2μ . Then the nickel line by the electron microanalyser should not go down or up suddenly at the edges of the nickel but have certain gradient as shown in thick line in Fig. 2b, even if the boundary between nickel and carbon would be very sharp and clear. When the nickel layer was thinner than the diameter of the electron beam spot, the height of the nickel peak should not show 100%. Then the height of the nickel line from the model should be shown as the thick line in Fig. 2b. As this model agrees well with the result of the electron probe microanalyser, the white ring in the fibre would be pure nickel metal (4).

X-ray analysis was carried out to observe the structural change of carbon fibres accompanied by holding at high temperature as shown in Fig. 3, (4). A sharp peak with higher angle than the low and broad peak of original fibre appeared and the peak became higher, and the peak of original fibre disappears accompanied by holding at high temperature. Any compounds of carbon and nickel could not be found from the diffraction patterns by a Debye camera and a roter flex all over the angle.

It is definitely shown from the results of Photo 2 and Figs. 2 and 3, that graphitization of the carbon fibre did not proceed gradually all over the fibre but proceeded suddenly at micro area with catalytic reaction by nickel, and the micro area extends all over the fibre. The migration rate of the nickel ring, i.e. graphitization rate of carbon fibre by nickel, was observed on many fibres in the yarn of each holding time (1). Though there were some differences of the rates among the fibres, general tendency was found as shown in Fig. 4. It is approximately proportional to square root of holding time. The non-linearity should be caused by increasing the thickness of the nickel ring accompanied by migration into the center of the carbon fibre.

It is very difficult to confirm the rate determining step of graphitization on carbon fibre, as the diameter of the fibre is very thin as 8μ and the rate of migration is not linear to holding time. Moreover, it is known that the direction of the crystallite axes are random in the cross section of the fibre. Then the migration rates of nickel in ab- and c-axes directions of carbon structure cannot be divided on the fibre.

On the reaction between nickel and carbon, the pyrolytic carbon will be able to simplify to analyse some problems mentioned above. Nickel was coated electrolytically at the condition of 0.2 Amp./dm^2 , and the thickness of the coated nickel layer was about 1μ . Nickel coated pyrolytic carbon was heat treated at 800°C and 1200°C for 20 minutes and 48 hours under 2×10^{-5} Torr. Nickel layer which consisted of many islands, migrated into the carbon, and original pyrolytic carbon was changed over flaky by migrating nickel layer as same as the case of carbon fibre. This flaky area should be the graphitized carbon deduced from the results about carbon fibre. Then the migration rate of nickel layer is proportional to the holding time at each temperature as shown in Fig. 5, (5). The thickness of the nickel layer did not decrease uniformly, but islands in the layer were remained gradually in the flaky area as many particles accompanied by migration of them. Thus the total amount of migrating nickel layer decreases gradually.

Arrhenius plot of the gradients of the migration rates showed a straight line, and it means that the graphitization should be caused by only one activation process. The activation energy from the result was 39.7 kcal/mol , and it agrees well with the value of

the activation energy 38.5 - 40.0 kcal/mol for diffusion of carbon atoms through nickel. Then the rate determining process of the graphitization should be the diffusion of carbon atoms through nickel (5).

As both sides of the nickel layer in carbon fibre or pyrolytic carbon, however, were carbons, driving force of the diffusion of carbon atoms from low graphitized area to more graphitized area cannot be considered simply with gradient of concentration of carbon in nickel. Therefore difference of free energy between two carbons at both sides of the nickel layer should be considered instead of concentration. The difference should be caused from the stability given by carbon structure (6). Then Fick's first law should be converted as follows:

$$J = A \cdot \frac{dG}{dx} \cdot \exp \left(- \frac{Q}{kT} \right)$$

where

J = flux of carbon atoms

$\frac{dG}{dx}$ = gradient of free energy of carbon in nickel

Q = activation energy for carbon atoms to diffuse through nickel

A = constant

In the equation, gradient of free energy is used instead of gradient of concentration of carbon. A and Q should be constant on the carbon-nickel system, and the gradient of the free energy would be deduced from the thickness of the nickel layer and difference of stabilities between two carbons. The stability would be presented by the parameter of inter-layer spacing of carbons.

According to above consideration, initial formation of the nickel ring in the fibre and of the layer in the pyrolytic carbon and their migration can be expressed as follows (6): there are many crystallites having various lattice spacing in the original carbon. Crystallites having narrower spacing should have lower free energy than wider ones. When the nickel coated carbon which includes many crystallites is held at high temperature, crystallites of wider spacing dissolve more swiftly than the others. Carbon atoms, dissolving from carbon surface into nickel, reach their equilibrium state with carbon atoms depositing from nickel on carbon surface. The saturating state should have slight difference locally among crystallites each other, i.e. less graphitized area dissolves more easily on graphitized area. As carbon atoms in nickel should deposit to be apt to reduce free energy, deposited carbon should be more graphitized than dissolving crystallites. Then crystallites of deposited carbon will grow at more graphitized crystallites in original carbon

fibre. On such state, the parts of wider spacing will be the sources and the narrower ones will be the sinks of carbon atoms for the diffusion of carbon atoms through nickel. Graphitized crystallites grow in the nickel and reach to certain height determined by growing rate of the graphitized crystallites and the diffusion rate of carbon atoms. After that, the crystallites will grow in the parallel direction to the carbon surface, and each nickel divided with grown graphites is constricted at its neck. (Photo 3 and its model.) Finally, a part of nickel is cut off from its mother layer as a little island. The inner side of the nickel island touches with original carbon and the outer side touches with graphitized carbon. Then the carbon atoms of original state dissolve into nickel from the inner part and deposit as graphite to the outer side so the nickel island receives certain force to migrate inside of the carbon.

Thus the carbon fibre is graphitized by nickel. The bonding force of intercrystallites in graphitized carbon is very weak, and nickel particles are dispersed in the flaky area as a heterogeneous phase and it was found from X-ray diffraction that preferred orientation of the graphite is not good. Then the graphitized carbon fibre is deteriorated accompanied by graphitization.

An attempt to prevent from reaction between carbon and nickel, was carried out on surface oxidized carbon fibre. On the fibre after holding at 1000°C for 1 hour, no reaction was found from scanning electron microscopic observation, X-ray diffraction analysis and electron probe microanalysis (1). Then it is important to prevent from the reaction between reinforcing fibre and matrix metal with some techniques such as oxidation of the carbon fibre, coating some materials on the surface of the fibre or alloying of the matrix to decrease dissolution of carbon atoms to make some good composite materials.

IV. Conclusions.

- 1) Migration of a nickel ring into carbon fibre was found on nickel coated carbon fibre after holding at high temperature. Carbon passed by nickel was graphitized and it showed flaky appearance.
- 2) Migration rate of nickel into carbon was approximately proportional to square root of holding time at high temperature on carbon fibre, meanwhile it was proportional to holding time on pyrolytic carbon.
- 3) Activation energy of graphitization by nickel was 39.7 kcal/mol, and it agrees well with the value of activation energy of diffusion of carbon atoms through nickel.
- 4) The diffusion of carbon atoms through nickel should be caused not by simple gradient of concentration of carbon atoms, but by

difference of free energy between two types of carbon.

- 5) The nickel ring should be formed initially by diffusion of carbon atoms from low graphitized crystallites in carbon fibre to more graphitized crystallites and growth of graphite at those crystallites should cut off a part of nickel from the coated nickel layer.
- 6) Strength of carbon fibre coated with nickel decreased after holding at high temperature.
- 7) It is important to prevent from the reaction between reinforcing fibre and matrix metal to make some good composite materials.

References

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Fig. 1. Strength of the heat treated carbon fibres coated with nickel.

Fig. 2a. Nickel intensity by an electron probe microanalyser on carbon fibre after holding at 800°C for 1 hour.

2b. A model for Fig. 2a.
 The thin line is a model distribution of nickel in carbon fibre deduced from Photo 2.
 The thick line is nickel intensity which should be caused by nickel distribution shown as the thin line.

Fig. 3. X-ray diffraction profiles of carbon (CO₂) on nickel coated carbon fibre after holding at high temperature. (by Cu K α)

Fig. 4. Ratio of the radius of the reacted area to the radius of the carbon fibre. Each curve, convex to the right, shows the frequency curve of the ratio in each stage.

Thickness of Reacted Pyrolytic Carbon

Fig. 5. Thickness of pyrolytic carbon reacted with nickel after holding at high temperature.

Photo 1. Carbon fibre with uniform and compact nickel layer.

Photo 2. Nickel coated carbon fibre held at 800°C for 1 hour. A part of the nickel layer reacted with carbon fibre is found as a white ring. (x 4000)
(by scanning electron microscope)

Photo 3. Initial state of graphitization in the nickel layer and a model for the photo.

Graphitization should grow as a broken line at more graphitized crystallites (shown as dots) in original carbon fibre. Carbon atoms should flow as the arrows. Graphite should grow in the direction parallel to the surface of carbon fibre after short time as thick line.